

Some Interesting Reactions of Gelomulides, the Natural Diterpene Lactones^{ψ#}

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Some interesting chemical reactions involving the characteristic features and confirming the proposed stereostructures of gelomulides A-F (1-6), the closely related diterpene lactones from the leaves of *Gelonium multiflorum* (Fam. Euphorbiaceae) and some chemical correlations were carried out. Thus, 3 upon treatment with DDQ gave 4 which was also produced when 6 was treated with pyridine or methanolic NaHCO₃. Zn dust/AcOH (reflux) or PPh₃/I₂ deepoxidized 1 and 4 to 13 and 14 respectively. PPh₃/I₂ converted 6 to the corresponding olefin 15 which upon refluxing with pyridine afforded 14, also obtained directly from 6 by refluxing with Zn dust/AcOH. NaBH₄ reduction of 3 and 6 gave the corresponding tetrahydro derivatives 18 and 21; additionally, 1 and 6 gave 19 and 20 respectively. Compound 1 underwent base-catalyzed opening of the lactone and the epoxide rings, followed by ring C aromatization to give 16. Similarly, under three different acidic conditions, 4 and 6 gave the same product 17. Catalytic hydrogenation of different gelomulides caused the hydrogenolysis of the allylic epoxide bond and reduction of the Δ^{1,2} bond (if present) but the 3-CO group remained unaffected. The formation of the products have been rationalized in terms of the assigned stereostructures and molecular conformations of the gelomulides.

Recently, six new diterpene lactones designated gelomulides A-F (1-6) sharing the same ent-abietane basic skeleton but differently substituted along the periphery of the molecules were isolated¹ in our laboratory from the leaves of an Euphorbiaceae plant *Gelonium multiflorum* A. Juss, collected from the neighbourhood of Calcutta. Their stereostructures were deduced¹ mainly from their ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr, ir and mass spectral characteristics, but adequate chemical support could not be provided earlier due to paucity of materials. Isolation and structures of four more new gelomulides G-J have also been reported²⁻⁴.

We now report some interesting reactions of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6 isolated in further quantities from a fresh supply of plant material, with reagents specific for functional groups present in their molecules. Moreover, their structural commonality prompted us to study some interconversions also.

Results and Discussion

It was reported¹ earlier that during the electron impact mass fragmentation the molecular ion (M⁺ 338) of 6 underwent thermal elimination of the elements of acetic acid to form the molecular ion (M⁺ 328) of 4 and thereafter showed the same fragmentation as 4. This elimination was chemically achieved when 6 was treated with pyridine under reflux for 3 h to produce 4 in almost quantitative yield. Such facile elimination was operative through E-2 mechanism and involved the *trans*-diaxial arrangement the vicinal eliminating groups of 1β-acetoxy and 2α-H, the

driving force being the formation of the α,β-unsaturated keto system (ν_{max} 1665 cm⁻¹) of 4, thus confirming the 1β-acetoxy (axial) configuration of 6, as suggested earlier from the narrow half-width (W_{1/2}) of its H-1 signal (δ 5.03, W_{1/2} ≈ 8 Hz). This 1,2-diaxial elimination is so facile that an attempt to deacetylate 6 even under a very mild condition using methanolic NaHCO₃ at room temperature failed and resulted in the formation of 4. The conversion under this condition was very slow and was complete after 5 days.

The epoxide function is a common structural feature of the gelomulides. Its presence, indirectly indicated from spectral data, requires chemical support. Action of BF₃-etherate on some gelomulides has been reported¹ earlier. Some experiments have now been carried out to open the epoxide and also to deepoxidize the molecules.

Catalytic hydrogenation [H₂/Pd-C (10%), EtOH] of 1, 3 and 6 effected the hydrogenolysis of the epoxide moiety to give the corresponding 8β-hydroxy-14-deoxy derivatives 8, 9 and 10; under this condition the Δ^{1,2} bond of 4 was also reduced to produce the same product 9 as obtained from 3. The hydrogenolysis of the 14-O bond occurred in the expected manner, the H atoms attacking the resulting less substituted as well as allylic C-14 radical and the 8-O radical from the β-face in a *cis*-fashion. Likewise, the hydrogenolysis of both 8,14β- and 11,12α-epoxide functions of 2 and jolkinolide (7) took place under similar catalytic hydrogenation to form the corresponding 8,11α-

^ψDedicated to Professor T R Govindachari on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary with profound regards

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dihydroxy derivatives **11** and **12** having *S*-configuration at both C-11 and C-12. Signals due to H-12 which were absent in **2** and **7** appeared in the hydrogenolysis products **11** and **12** at δ 5.58 and 5.56 (both m, $W_{1/2} \approx 13$ Hz). The downfield shift of H-12 in **11** and **12** compared to the H-12 (appearing in the region δ 4.81–5.07) in **1**, **2**, **4**, **6** and the hydrogenolysis products **8**, **9**, and **10**, calls for an explanation. This is probably due to the anisotropic deshielding effect (*cf. peri* effect) of 11α -OH on H-12 since the 11-O and 12-H bonds are nearly coplanar (**11a** and **12a**)*, as observed with their Dreiding models. The regio- and stereospecific hydrogenolysis of the 11,12 α -epoxy function may be ascribed to the *cis* and α -hydrogenation of the epoxy oxygen and the more stable (though more substituted) C-12 allylic radical, stabilized also by the adjacent lactonic ether oxygen. It is evident from the Dreiding models of **11a*** and **12a*** that the molecules of both **11** and **12** attain chair-twist boat-planar lactone conformation with *trans-transoid-cis* configuration of the perhydrophenanthrene moiety (A, B, C rings).

A combination of zinc dust and glacial acetic acid is employed for the conversion of epoxides to the corresponding olefins^{5,6}. Compound **1** gave the 8,14-olefinic compound **13** when refluxed with Zn dust and glacial acetic acid for 3 h. The molecular formula of the product **13** has one oxygen atom less than that of the parent compound **1**. The ¹H nmr spectrum of **13** lacks the epoxy proton and its ¹³C nmr spectrum lacks the original oxygenated *sp*³ carbons at δ 60.9 and 56.1; instead, one olefinic proton at δ 6.29, one monoprotonated (C-14) and one nonprotonated (C-8) olefinic carbons at δ 114.28 and 151.58 respectively, are discernible in the spectrum. Compounds **4** and **6** also got deepoxidized upon similar treatment, and the nmr spectral features have been changed as in the case of **1**. Interestingly, the product **14** was obtained from both **4** and **6**, indicating thereby the formation of a double bond across C-1 and C-2, through the diaxial elimination of the elements of acetic acid in case of **6**.

Deepoxidation has also been achieved using triphenylphosphine^{7,8} in presence of iodine under nitrogen blanket.

In **11a** and **12a** ring C is viewed from the bottom side with both H-12 and 11-OH appearing β - to the observer

Triphenylphosphine is a good nucleophile and a weak base. These properties are utilized in the Wittig reagent. The participation of the *d*-orbitals of phosphorus in the triphenylphosphine is playing a vital role. In case of deoxygenation of the epoxide leading to the olefin, probably complexation takes place through the participation of *d*-orbitals of phosphorus and lone-pair of oxygen. This is followed by the collapse of the complex by way of the formation of the olefin and triphenylphosphonium oxide, the whole process being activated by iodine (Scheme 1). At least part of the driving force for this reaction is the formation of the very stable P^+-O^- bond as in the tertiary phosphine oxide. This formulation implies an expansion of the phosphorus octet and the orbital overlap with phosphorus *3d* atomic orbitals.

Scheme 1 Reagents PPh_3/I_2 in CH_2Cl_2 , N_2 , 3 h (~75%)

In cases of **1** and **4**, the PPh_3/I_2 reaction products (**13**, **14**) are identical with those obtained by Zn dust/AcOH reaction. However, unlike **1** and **4**, **6** gave two different compounds (**14**, **15**) when treated independently with Zn dust/AcOH and PPh_3/I_2 . In the reaction of **6** with PPh_3/I_2 , the OAc group at C-1 survived and no double bond was formed to give **15**. However, **15** on treatment with pyridine under reflux gave **14**.

Alkaline hydrolysis of **1** furnished an aromatic compound ($M^+ 332$) in which acetyl group was hydrolyzed and ring C got aromatized at the expense of the epoxide to yield a phenolic acid (**16**) ($M^+ 332$). Its 1H nmr spectrum was quite revealing. Two aromatic *para*-protons were observed at δ 6.76 and 6.78 as broad singlets (H-11 and H-14), and H-15 appeared as a multiplet and the methyl at C-15 as a broad singlet. The benzylic protons at C-7 appeared at δ 2.92–2.75 as multiplets and the hydroxymethine proton at C-3 appeared at δ 3.51 ($W_{1/2} \approx 9$ Hz). The formation of **16** is mechanistically interesting (Scheme 2).

Compound **4** on treatment with 6 *N* HCl in methanol furnished, instead of the expected 8,14-diol, an aromatic compound (**17**) ($M^+ 310$). The aromatic protons were observed at δ 7.42 (br s, H-14) and 6.87 (s, H-11), the C-7 benzylic protons at δ 2.85–2.73 and the C-15 methyl protons at δ 1.12 (d, J 3.6 Hz). Compound **17** was also obtained when **4** and **6** were treated separately with conc. H_2SO_4 at low temperature ($\approx 5^\circ$) or with glacial acetic acid containing a little perchloric acid. Ring C underwent aromatization perhaps as follows. The protonated epoxide func-

Scheme 2 Reagents 3% KOH/MeOH, $N_2 \Delta$, 1.5 h (60%)

tion opened up by the attack of H_2O at C-14 to form a 1,2-glycol system. The 8-OH after protonation was eliminated as H_2O generating a carbocation at C-8 which collapsed to an olefin through the loss of H-9. This was followed by acid-catalyzed 1,4-elimination of water and the resulting homoannular diene aromatized through the loss of H-12 and picking up of a proton at C-15 making the 15-methyl secondary. However, the stereochemistry at this centre could not be ascertained (Scheme 3).

Treatment of **3** with sodium borohydride in methanol gave a tetrahydro derivative (**18**) in which both the keto carbonyl and the double bond of the α, β -unsaturated γ -lactone

Scheme 3 Reagents 6 *N* HCl/MeOH, rt, 24 h (48%) or conc H_2SO_4 , 0° , 0.5 h (50%) or gl AcOH/ $HClO_4$, rt, 24 h (56%)

moiety got reduced (spectral evidence). Gelomulide A (1) gave a dihydro derivative 19 in poor yield when its sodium borohydride reduction was carried out in methanol under nitrogen blanket. On borohydride reduction, 6 gave 20 and 21; in both the products C-3 carbonyl and the double bond of the α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone of 6 suffered reduction. However, in 21 the C-1 acetate survived while in 20 the acetate suffered hydrolysis leading to the 1,3-diol system (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Reagent : $\text{NaBH}_4/\text{MeOH}$, 5–10°, N_2 , 18 h (40%).

On treatment with DDQ for 30 h, 3 was converted to 4 in a poor yield.

Experimental

M.ps. measured in open capillary tubes are uncorrected. Uv spectra were taken in EtOH and ir spectra as KBr pellets. Petrol refers to b.p. 60–80° fraction. The silica gel (60–120 mesh, Glaxo) was used for column chromatography; silica gel (230–400 mesh, SRL) was used for flash chromatography in a Eylea EFC-2000 instrument. To monitor fractions, tlc experiments were done using microscopic slides with silica gel G layers put on them by dipping in its chloroform slurry, taking out and drying in ambient temperature; similar fractions were combined. ^1H nmr spectra (at 300 HMz) and ^{13}C nmr spectra (at 75 MHz) were recorded in CDCl_3 in a Bruker-300A instrument. All air-sensitive reactions were run under N_2 in flame-dried glassware with magnetic stirring. The products were characterized by ir,

^1H nmr, ^{13}C nmr, and mass (70 eV) spectral analyses.

Catalytic hydrogenation of gelomulides A-D and F : Hydrogen gas was passed through an absolute alcoholic solution of the respective gelomulides in presence of 10% Pd-C at atmospheric pressure and room temperature for 5–8 h. After the removal of the catalyst by filtration, the products were obtained from the filtrates by evaporation and were purified by crystallization from suitable solvent or solvent systems.

Gelomulide A (1) furnished compound 8 : Compound 8, (80%), m.p. 248°, reaction time 8 h, R_f 0.60, CHCl_3 : MeOH (93 : 3, v/v); ν_{max} 3515 (O–H), 2930 (C–H), 1745 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1720 and 1240 (acetate C=O and OC–O), 1675, 1440, 1367, 1045, 1017, 970, 910, 760 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 5.07 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 22$ Hz, H-12), 4.74 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 8$ Hz, H-3), 2.84 and 2.62 (2H, d, J 14 Hz, H₂-14), 2.52 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 20$ Hz, H-11), 2.06 (3H, s, 3-OCOCH₃), 2.02–1.26 (11H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.87 (3H, d, J 2Hz, 15-CH₃), 1.1, 0.96, 0.92 (3H, s each, 3 × t-CH₃); ^{13}C nmr δ 37.43 (C-1), 22.73 (C-2), 77.79 (C-3), 38.44 (C-4), 49.72 (C-5), 19.41 (C-6), 34.48 (C-7), 74.30 (C-8), 56.62 (C-9), 36.59 (C-10), 28.95 (C-11), 77.29 (C-12), 160.08 (C-13), 43.09 (C-14), 123.67 (C-15), 175.0 (C-16), 8.22 (C-17), 28.28 (C-18), 21.94 (C-19), 18.09 (C-20), 170.40 (3-OCOCH₃), 21.14 (3-OCOCH₃)

Gelomulide B (2) furnished compound 11 : Compound 11, (67%), m.p. 260°, reaction time 6 h, R_f 0.3 (CHCl_3 : MeOH, 19 : 1); ν_{max} 3450, 3410 (O–H), 2920 (C–H), 1750 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1720 and 1250 (acetate C=O and OC–O), 1674, 1443, 1367, 1050, 1015 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 5.58 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 13$ Hz, H-12), 4.66 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 8$ Hz, H-3), 3.57 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 12$ Hz, H-11), 2.8–2.46 (2H, m, H₂-14), 2.07 (3H, s, 3-OCOCH₃), 2.14–1.24 (10H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.8 (3H, br s, 15-CH₃), 0.87, 0.63 (6H and 3H respectively, s each, 3 × t-CH₃).

Gelomulide D (4) furnished compound 9 : Compound 9, (80%), m.p. 212°, reaction time 6 h, R_f 0.50 (CHCl_3 : MeOH, 93 : 3); ν_{max} 3470 (O–H), 2920 (C–H), 1750 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1705 (ketone C=O), 1455, 1345, 1310, 1247, 1120, 1035, 980 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 4.9 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 24 Hz, H-12), 2.88 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 24$ Hz, H-2), 2.88–2.6 (3H, m, H-11 and H₂-14), 2.24 (1H, m, $W_{1/2} \approx 28$ Hz, H-2), 2.18 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, H-9), 2.07–1.46 (8H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.83 (3H, d, J 2 Hz, 15-CH₃), 1.39, 1.1, 0.98 (3H, s each, 3 × t-CH₃ at C-4 (*gem*) and C-10); ^{13}C nmr δ 42.57 (C-1), 32.39 (C-2), 215.80 (C-3), 56.32 (C-4), 56.32 (C-5), 20.31 (C-6), 37.28 (C-7), 74.56 (C-8), 48.15 (C-9), 35.39 (C-10), 30.77 (C-11), 77.91 (C-12), 155.96 (C-13), 41.56 (C-14), 126.5[#] (C-15), 174.94 (C-16), 8.16 (C-17), 31.55 (C-18), 22.91 (C-19), 17.27.

Gelomulide C (3) furnished compound 9 : Compound 9, m.p. 212° (reaction time 4 h), was found to be identical with that obtained from gelomulide D (4).

Gelomulide F (6) furnished compound 10 : Compound 10, (80%), m.p. 225°, reaction time 5 h, R_f 0.45 (CHCl₃ : MeOH, 19 : 1, v/v); ν_{\max} 3510 (O-H), 2920 (C-H), 1745 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1715 and 1245 (acetate C=O and OC-O), 1695 (ketone C=O), 1380, 1025, 915 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 5.04 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 8 Hz, H-1), 4.88 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 24 Hz, H-12), 3.12 (1H, dd, J 13 and 3 Hz, H-2), 2.75-2.6 (3H, m, H-11 and H₂-14), 2.33 (1H, dd, J 13 and 4 Hz, H-2), 2.25 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, H-9), 2.68-1.44 (6H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 2.00 (3H, s, 1-OCOCH₃), 1.83 (3H, d, J 2 Hz, 15-CH₃), 1.39, 1.17, 0.94 (3H, s each, 3 \times t-CH₃).

Jolkmolide B (7) furnished compound 12 : Compound 12, (67%), m.p. 220-21°, R_f 0.55 (CHCl₃ : methanol, 99 : 1); ν_{\max} 3450, 3410 (O-H), 2920 (C-H), 2920 (C-H), 1744 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1680, 1440, 1380, 1020 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 5.56 (1H, m, H-12), 3.56 (1H, dd, J 8 and 3 Hz, H-11), 2.78-2.42 (2H, m, H₂-14), 2.34-1.02 (12H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.78 (3H, d, J 2 Hz, 15-CH₃), 0.89, 0.78, 0.59 (3H, s each, 3 \times t-CH₃).

Reactions of gelomulides A, D and F with Zn dust/ AcOH : Gelomulide was refluxed with Zn dust (1 : 1.2 mmol) in glacial acetic acid for 3 h. The solid thus obtained was washed with 30% aqueous NH₄Cl followed by water. The residue left was then dissolved in CHCl₃ and chromatographed to afford the desired compound.

Gelomulide A furnished compound 13 : Compound 13 was crystallized from CHCl₃-petrol as colourless needles, (66%), m.p. 228-29°, [α]_D + 340.7 (CHCl₃, c 0.054); λ_{\max} 275 nm (log ϵ 4.38); ν_{\max} 2940 (C-H), 1745 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1725 and 1250 (acetate C=O and OC-O), 1660 (conjugated C=C), 1430, 1370, 1300, 1180, 1080, 1040, 1020, 975, 865 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 6.29 (1H, s, H-14), 4.88 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 24 Hz, H-12), 4.70 (1H, br s, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 8 Hz, H-3), 2.57 (1H, dd, J 13.5 and 6.2 Hz, H-7a), 2.53 (1H, m, H-7e), 2.30 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, H-9), 2.26 (1H, m, H-11a), 2.08 (3H, s, 3-OCOCH₃), 1.80 (3H, br s, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 8 Hz, 15-CH₃), 1.81-1.40 (m, CH₂ and CH), 0.97, 0.94, 0.90 (each 3H, s, 3 \times t-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ 32.83 (C-1), 23.26 (C-2)^a, 77.65 (C-3), 41.21 (C-4), 51.60 (C-5)^b, 23.18 (C-6)^a, 36.92 (C-7), 151.58 (C-8), 49.64 (C-9)^b, 36.9 (C-10), 27.54 (C-11), 75.87 (C-12), 155.92 (C-13), 114.27 (C-14), 116.56 (C-15), 175.14 (C-16), 8.25 (C-17), 28.30 (C-18), 21.19 (C-19), 16.69 (C-20), 170.42 (OC OCH₃), 21.91 (OCOCH₃).

Gelomulide D furnished compound 14 : Compound 14 was crystallized from CHCl₃-petrol as colourless needles, (47%), m.p. 232°, [α]_D + 242° (CHCl₃, c 0.058); λ_{\max} 273

nm (log ϵ 4.36); ν_{\max} 2930 (C-H), 1730 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1665 (α,β -unsaturated C=O), 1425, 1310, 1245, 1080, 1015, 850, 805 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 6.40 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-1), 6.36 (1H, s, H-14), 5.81 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-2), 4.79 (1H, dd, J 15 and 6 Hz, H-12), 3.00 (1H, dd, J 14.2, 6.3 Hz, H-7a), 2.79 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-9), 2.54 (1H, m, H-7e), 2.21-2.12 (1H, m, H-11a), 1.94 (1H, m, H-11e), 1.84 (3H, br s, 15-CH₃), 1.80-1.50 (m, CH₂ and CH), 1.24, 1.12, 1.11 (each 3H, s, 3 \times t-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ 155.0 (C-1), 124.23 (C-2), 204.77 (C-3), 51.74 (C-4), 50.28 (C-5), 24.42 (C-6), 30.17 (C-7)^a, 150.25 (C-8), 43.09 (C-9), 36.47 (C-10), 36.70 (C-11)^a, 76.21 (C-12), 154.96 (C-13), 115.26 (C-14), 116.89 (C-15), 174.95 (C-16), 8.17 (C-17), 31.38 (C-18), 22.17 (C-19), 15.71 (C-20).

Gelomulide F furnished compound 14 : Compound 14 (37%) was found to be identical (superimposable ir, m.p. and m.m.p.) with that obtained from gelomulide D.

Treatment of gelomulides A, D and F with PPh₃/I₂ : Gelomulide (1.0 mmol) was added to a magnetically stirred solution of PPh₃ (1.0 mmol) in dichloromethane containing iodine (2.0 mmol) and the stirring was continued for 3 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was then washed with 20% aqueous Na₂S₂O₃ solution to remove excess iodine and then passed through a column of silica gel. After removal of the excess solvent, the residue obtained was crystallized from CHCl₃-petrol to afford the desired product.

Geomulide A furnished compound 13 : Compound 13, (75%), m.p. 228° (CHCl₃-petrol), was found to be identical (m.m.p. superimposable ir) with that obtained from gelomulide A on treatment with Zn-dust-acetic acid.

Gelomulide D furnished compound 14 : Compound 14, (73%), m.p. 230-32° (chloroform-petrol), was found to be identical with that obtained from gelomulide D on treatment with Zn-dust-acetic acid.

Gelomulide F furnished compound 15 : Compound 15, (75%), m.p. 198°, [α]_D + 235.5° (CHCl₃, c 0.058); λ_{\max} 273 nm (log ϵ 4.35); ν_{\max} 2960 (C-H), 1745 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1240 (acetate O-CO), 1715 (C=O), 1670 (conjugated C=C), 1435, 1372, 1085, 1055, 1020, cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 6.34 (1H, s, H-14), 5.01 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 8 Hz, H-1), 4.73 (1H, m, H-12), 3.19 (1H, dd, J 13.4, 2.4 Hz, H-2), 2.81 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-9), 2.62 (1H, dd, J 14.3, 6.5 Hz, H-7a), 2.50 (1H, br d, H-7e), 2.35 (1H, dd, J 13.4, 3.5 Hz, H-2), 2.16 (1H, m, H-11e), 2.02 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 1.91-1.56 (m, CH₂ and CH), 1.81 (3H, br s, 15-CH₃), 1.28, 1.16, 0.93 (each 3H, s, 3 \times t-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ 80.98 (C-10), 39.93 (C-2), 210.68 (C-3), 55.70 (C-4), 52.13 (C-5), 29.87 (C-6), 36.58 (C-7), 149.97 (C-8), 44.08 (C-9), 37.45 (C-10), 23.22 (C-11), 75.99 (C-12), 154.95 (C-13), 115.67 (C-14), 117.07 (C-15), 174.98 (C-16), 8.21 (C-17), 27.55 (C-18), 20.63 (C-19), 14.67 (C-20), 169.90

*The assignments superscribed by a or b are exchangeable

(OCOCH₃), 21.65 (OCOCH₃).

Alkaline hydrolysis of gelomulide A. Formation of compound 16 : Gelomulide A (20 mg) was refluxed with 3% methanolic KOH for 1.5 h. The mixture was then neutralised with 2 N HCl and extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄, and evaporated under reduced pressure. The concentrate obtained was chromatographed when the light petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluate furnished a colourless crystalline compound (10 mg), m.p. 179°, M⁺ 332; ν_{\max} 3440 (O-H), 2960 (C-H), 1690 (carboxylic acid C=O), 1630, 1575, 1500 (aromatic), 1390, 1265, 1226, 1070, 920, 870 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 6.78 (1H, s, H-11), 6.76 (1H, s, H-14), 3.87 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 25 Hz, H-15), 3.51 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 9 Hz, H-3), 2.92–2.75 (2H, m, H₂-7), 2.58–1.89 (5H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.74 (3H, br s, 15-CH₃), 1.01, 0.97, 0.93 (3H, s each, 3 \times t-CH₃).

Treatment of gelomulide D with acid. Formation of compound 17 : Gelomulide D (20 mg) was treated with 6 N HCl in MeOH and kept at room temperature for 24 h. It was then poured into water, and methanol was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with ether and washed with water until free from acid and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed and a colourless compound was obtained. It was crystallized from chloroform-light petrol mixture to give pure 17 (9.5 mg), m.p. 184°, M⁺ 310; ν_{\max} 2945 (C-H), 1800 (benzylic lactone C=O), 1675, 1638, 1485 (aromatic), 1220, 1110, 1010, 865, 770 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 7.42 (1H, s, H-14), 6.87 (1H, s, H-11), 6.46 (1H, d, J 10.2 Hz, H-1), 5.87 (1H, d, J 10.2 Hz, H-2), 3.67–3.59 (1H, m, H-15), 2.85–2.73 (2H, m, H₂-7), 2.11–1.69 (3H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.50, 1.48, 1.46 (3H, s each, 3 \times t-CH₃), 1.13 (3H, d, J 3.6 Hz, 15-CH₃).

Treatment of gelomulide F with conc. H₂SO₄. Formation of compound 17 : Gelomulide F (50 mg) was treated with conc. H₂SO₄ (1.5 ml) at 0° for 0.5 h. The resulting orange reaction mixture was poured in crushed ice (4 g), neutralised with NaHCO₃, and extracted with chloroform (3 \times 2 ml). The chloroform layer was separated, washed with water (2 \times 2 ml), and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The residue obtained after removal of chloroform, was chromatographed when a colourless compound (17) was obtained (25 mg, 50%). It was crystallized from chloroform-petrol mixture as colourless needles, m.p. 203°, [α]_D–276.2° (CHCl₃, c 0.054); λ_{\max} 285 (3.64), 206 nm (4.55); ν_{\max} 2920 (C-H), 1790 (benzylic lactone C=O), 1665, 1620, 1470 (aromatic C=C), 1410, 1360, 1205, 1100, 1050, 1000, 930, 850 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 7.42 (1H, s, H-14), 6.87 (1H, s, H-11), 6.46 (1H, d, J 9.9 Hz, H-1), 5.87 (1H, d, J 9.9 Hz, H-2), 3.67–3.59 (1H, m, H-15), 2.85–2.73 (2H,

m, H₂-7), 2.01–1.69 (3H, m, H₂-6 and H-5), 1.47, 1.13, 1.12 (3H each, s, 3 \times t-CH₃), 1.46 (3H, d, J 3.6 Hz, 15-CH₃).

Treatment of gelomulide F with perchloric acid. Formation of compound 17 : Gelomulide F (20 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1.5 ml) and 3 drops of perchloric acid was added to it. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature, then poured in ice-water (93 ml), neutralized with NaHCO₃, and extracted with chloroform (2 \times 3 ml). The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and after removal of the chloroform, the residue was chromatographed, when a compound (7 mg, 45%), m.p. 201° (chloroform-petrol), was obtained. It was found to be identical with compound 17 (m.m.p. co-tlc superimposable ir).

Treatment of gelomulide D with conc. H₂SO₄. Formation of compound 17 : Gelomulide D (40 mg) was treated with conc. H₂SO₄ (1 ml) at 0° for 0.5 h. The residue obtained after usual work-up as before, followed by chromatography yielded a compound (15 mg, 42%), m.p. 203°, which was found to be identical with all respects with compound 17.

Treatment of gelomulide-D with perchloric acid in glacial acetic acid. Formation of compound 17 : Gelomulide D (50 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and 4 drops of perchloric acid was added to it, and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 h. The residue obtained on usual work-up gave a product which was purified by chromatography and then crystallized from chloroform-petrol to afford compound 17 (28 mg, 60%), m.p. 203°.

Reduction of gelomulide C (3) with sodium borohydride in MeOH. Formation of compound 18 : Gelomulide C (20 mg) in MeOH was treated with sodium borohydride (50 mg) pinch by pinch for 1 h and then kept at room temperature overnight. The concentrate was extracted with chloroform, washed with water, dried, and crystallized from chloroform-light petrol mixture to furnish a colourless crystalline compound (8 mg), m.p. 180–183°, M⁺ 334; ν_{\max} 3440 (O-H), 2930 (C-H), 1770 (5-membered lactone C=O), 1445, 1158, 1050, 1012, 850 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 4.61 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 28 Hz, H-12), 3.8 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 9.3 Hz, H-3), 3.18 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, H-14), 2.88 (1H, d, J 7.13 and 3.5 Hz, H-15), 2.59–2.44 (2H, m), 2.17–1.19 (11H, m, saturated methylene and methine protons), 1.34 (3H, d, J 7.2 Hz, 15-CH₃), 0.95, 0.92, 0.90 (3H, s each, 3 \times t-CH₃).

Treatment of gelomulide A with NaBH₄. Formation of compound 19 : Under similar condition as above, gelomulide A (50 mg) was treated with NaBH₄ (100 mg) to yield compound 6 which was crystallized from chloroform-petrol as colourless needles (28%), m.p. 193°; ν_{\max} 2950 (C-H), 1760 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1740, 1240

(acetate C=O and O-CO), 1720, 1450, 1370, 1175, 1040, 1010 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 4.69 (1H, br s, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz, H-3), 4.65 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 18 Hz, H-12), 3.19 (1H, d, J 3.7 Hz, H-14), 2.87 (1H, m, H-13), 2.58 (1H, m, H-11), 2.08 (3H, s, 3-OCOCH₃), 2.03–1.42 (m, CH₂ and CH), 1.35 (3H, d, J 7.2 Hz, 15-CH₃), 0.98, 0.96, 0.90 (each 3H, s, 3 \times t-CH₃).

Treatment of gelomulide F with NaBH₄ Formation of compound 20 : To gelomulide F (100 mg) dissolved in methanol (25 ml), NaBH₄ (200 mg) was added slowly at low temperature (5–10°) under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight at room temperature. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure, the concentrate was taken in water and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. The residue was purified through column chromatography to yield a colourless compound (5) which was crystallized from chloroform-petrol, (20 mg) m.p. 243°; ν_{max} 3500, 3400 (OH), 2930 (C–H), 1740 (α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone C=O), 1450, 1390, 1210, 1080, 1025, 980, 855 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 4.61 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ \approx 24 Hz, H-12), 3.81 (1H, br s, H-3), 3.62 (1H, br s, H-1), 3.20 (1H, d, J 3.7 Hz, H-14), 2.85 (1H, m, H-13), 2.61 (1H, d, J 6.2 Hz, H-9), 2.54 (1H, m, H-11), 2.05–1.60 (m, CH₂ and CH), 1.35 (3H, d, J 7.1 Hz, 15-CH₃), 1.06, 0.92, 0.91 (each 3H, s, 3 \times t-CH₃).

Conversion of compound 15 to compound 14 : Compound 15 (20 mg) was refluxed with pyridine (2 ml) for 3 h. After usual work-up yielded a compound (16 mg, 91%), m.p. 232°, which was found to be identical in all respects with compound 14 (m.m.p., co-tlc, superimposable ir).

Treatment of gelomulide F with pyridine Formation of gelomulide D : Gelomulide F (50 mg) was dissolved in dry pyridine (1.5 ml) and refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in crushed ice, acidified with dilute HCl (2 N), and extracted with chloroform (3 \times 2 ml). The chloroform extract was washed with water (3 \times 1.5 ml) saturated with NaCl, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to obtain gelomulide D, crystallizing from chloroform-petrol mixture as colourless needles (42 mg, 98%), m.p. 224° (m.m.p., co-tlc, superimposable ir with an authentic sample).

The reaction was repeated with more gelomulide F (300 mg) to prepare more GM-D (250 mg).

Treatment of gelomulide F with NaHCO₃ Formation of gelomulide D : Gelomulide F (50 mg) in methanol (6 ml) was treated with NaHCO₃ (10 mg) at room temperature for 5 days. Methanol was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with chloroform (3 \times 2 ml). The extract was dried over anhydrous

Na₂SO₄ and evaporated. The concentrate thus obtained was chromatographed to give gelomulide-D (11 mg, 26%) which was crystallized from chloroform-petrol as colourless needles, m.p. 224°. Unreacted gelomulide F was recovered from the later eluates of the chromatogram.

Dehydrogenation of gelomulide C (3) by DDQ in dry dioxane Formation of gelomulide D (4) : Gelomulide C (20 mg) in dry dioxane was refluxed with a pinch of DDQ reagent for 30 h and then the whole mixture was passed through a column of alumina gel. The eluate was concentrated and chromatographed. The light petrol-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) eluate afforded a compound (6 mg), m.p. 220°, which was found to be identical with gelomulide D (m.m.p., co-tlc, superimposable ir).

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